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with International Participation

CHEMISTRY, PHYSICS AND TECHNOLOGY OF SURFACE

devoted to
40th anniversary of the
Chuiko Institute of Surface Chemistry
of NAS of Ukraine

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Тези доповідей Всеукраїнської конференції з міжнародною участю “Хімія, фізика і технологія поверхні”, присвяченій 40-річчю з дня заснування Інституту хімії поверхні ім. О.О. Чуйка НАН України – Київ, 2026. – 290 с.

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Збірник містить тези доповідей, які було представлено на конференції. Тематика конференції: теорія хімічної будови та реакційна здатність поверхні твердих тіл; фізико-хімія поверхневих та міжфазних явищ; хімія, фізика та технологія наноматеріалів; медико-біологічні та біохімічні аспекти вивчення наноматеріалів. Тези доповідей подано в авторській редакції.

The Book contains abstracts of the Conference presentations. The Conference topics: theory of chemical structure and reactivity of solid surfaces; physical chemistry of surface and interfacial phenomena; chemistry, physics and technology of nanomaterials; medical, biological and biochemical aspects of investigation of nanomaterials. The abstracts are published in the author's edition.

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Organic-inorganic perovskite/polymethine dye composite films: influence of formation conditions on optical properties

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The modern development of materials science and photonics is focused on the creation of functional materials with controllable optical and electronic properties. One of the most promising in this context is organic-inorganic perovskites, which are distinguished by high light absorption, tunable band gap, and efficient charge carrier transport. However, their stability and spectral absorption range are limited. Polymethine dyes, due to their intense absorption in the visible and near-IR ranges and delocalized π -system, are effective sensitizers. Their integration into perovskite structures can expand the spectral range and increase the efficiency of charge carrier generation and transport.

This work aims to create composite materials based on perovskite $\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3\text{PbI}_3$ modified with a polymethine dye indodicarbocyanine 5111 to expand spectral sensitivity and/or enhance absorption in the visible region, as well as to study the influence of formation conditions on their optical properties.

Perovskite films were obtained by spin-coating from a solution of the starting reagents (ratio $\text{PbI}_2:\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3\text{I}-1:2$) in DMSO with subsequent annealing at 190 °C for 15 minutes. To create composite films, dye 5111 was applied to the perovskite film and annealing was performed under different conditions: temperature (50-80 °C) and annealing time (5-15 min). Application of dye 5111 to perovskite, compared to pure perovskite, leads to increased absorption in the region of 500–750 nm (~680–690 nm – absorption band of the dye), and the band is broadened and bathochromically shifted. In the fluorescence spectra of composite films, compared to pure perovskite, there is a broadening of the emission band without a significant shift of the maximum (~795 nm), which is due to the overlap of the emission of perovskite and dye (~750–760 nm).

When the temperature increased from 50 to 70 °C, the maximum values of absorption and fluorescence were obtained, while at 80 °C, they decreased due to degradation or aggregation of the dye 5111. Increasing the annealing time from 5 to 10 min contributed to the increase in absorption, while a further increase to 15 min did not have a positive effect. At the same time, the fluorescence intensity of the composite films decreases with increasing annealing time.